

Emotional and Behavioural problems among Nigerian Children who had Experienced Violent Armed Attacks: Impact on Learning and Education

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ABSTRACT

Violent armed conflicts affect 1 in 10 children across the globe. These conflicts impact the emotional and behavioural regulation among affected children. These dysregulations complicate learning and education among children who had experienced violent armed conflict but information about this is scanty or non-existence in sub-Saharan African, especially Nigeria despite the insurgency across the country. This study evaluated the impact of armed conflict on the emotional and behavioural problems and its consequences on learning and education among Nigerian children who had witnessed violent armed conflicts. Parents and teachers of 117 pupils in a non-conventional school were interviewed through a consecutive sampling method. The interview was a face-to-face using the Socio-demographic questionnaire and the Strength and Difficulty questionnaire (SDQ) to collect data in North-East, Nigeria who had survived the 2018/19-armed attacks. The mean age of the pupils was 9.87 ± 2.85 , and 12% and 27% of the children had borderline/abnormal difficulties on the Total Difficulty Scores of the SDQ which rates emotional problems, peer relationship issues, conduct and behaviour, and activity level in a child, in relation to learning and education. The difference in the SDQ total mean scores rating between Parents and Teachers was not statistically significant ($t=0.103$, $p=0.913$). However, the mean score of impact of difficulties of the supplementary part of the SDQ for children 8 years and above was 22.72 ± 11.52 and 17.52 ± 11.52 in the two areas studied and it was statistically significant ($t=2.217$, $p=0.029$). Violent Armed attacks experienced by children impacts both emotional and behavioural regulation and this in turn affects learning, literacy, numeracy, education and fun, and play and arts at home and in school.

Keywords: Armed conflicts, Children, Education, Strength and difficulties questionnaire

INTRODUCTION

Repugnant violence by non-state actors is of grave consequences on the most vulnerable in the society and country. Violent extremism is as old as man and in

Nigeria it did not just start with the Boko Haram insurgency in 2009 but predates it. Violent extremism occurs on a daily bases in Nigeria and children and most

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affected. These violent armed attacks leave a trail of negative psychosocial consequences-emotional and behavioural, that affects arts, fun play, literacy and education of children in conventional schools talk less of non-conventional schools that are most often makeshift schools with no requisite infrastructures or learning tools to help the child navigate the learning processes and education.

Violent Extremism as defined by United Nations Organization for Education, Science and Culture (UNESCO) is 'the belief and actions of people who support or use violence to achieve ideological, religious or political or political goals'.¹ These conflicts are sources of stress in children and may imprint an undesirable stamp on their developing emotions, behaviours and personalities in ways which may be difficult to measure.² Children have immature coping mechanisms at various stages of life and as such they may rely on adults for understanding of external events.² Unfortunately, the loss of family and friends may shatter their world and influence their perception of self, others and the universe at large.² These reactions could be internalized or externalized which puts them at risk of emotional and behavioural disorders, loss of trust and neglect of school among others^{3,4}.

Furthermore, the mental representation of the trauma as an aftermath of violent attacks can result in an unconscious organizing belief that determines how children see the world and how they choose to act or relate with it.² This may result in the development of militaristic ideas that may in turn precipitate a cycle of violence (a conduct problem) in their life time⁵. However, others adopt a laudable attitude and adjust towards forgiveness and selflessness². The ability of a human being to survive, recover and persevere against various obstacles and threats known as resilience has been observed more in children^{3,4}. Therefore, the role of schools whether conventional or non-conventional, the family and the community at large has a positive impact in promoting resilience among children which will in turn promote recovery^{1,3} and promote social relationship as

exemplified in peer relationships.

Between the months of December 2017 and January 2018^{6,7,19}, Numan and Demsa Local Government Areas (LGAs) in Adamawa State, North East, Nigeria had a number of unpleasant experiences of violent armed attacks where a number of wards were attacked and life and properties destroyed^{6,7,8,19}. Schools were destroyed leading to creation of non-conventional schools by non-governmental organizations (NGOs) to provide learning and education, and to engage children in fun, plays, arts and to provide opportunities to maximize their potentials in the future. But the effects of the armed attacks on the emotions and behaviours negates the novel ventures by the NGOs. This informed the study which aimed at finding the prevalence of abnormalities in emotion, conduct, hyperactivity and peer relationship as a result of the aftermath of the armed attacks and on how these affects children learning, education, arts and plays in schools and at home. It also related the socio-demographic of the children to emotional and behavioural problems among Nigerian children who had witness or experienced violent armed conflict which to the best of our knowledge has not been studied in Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study location

The study was conducted in Dong and Kikan wards of Demsa and Numan Local Government Areas (LGAs) of Adamawa state, North Eastern Nigeria. The two wards were purposively selected because of the ongoing Partners West Africa Nigeria (PWAN) project. PWAN project is a non-governmental (NGO) program saddled with the promotion of good governance, accountability and transparency by expanding opportunities for citizen's engagement. Demsa Local government has an area of 1,825 km² with a population of about 238, 400, projected with 2006 census figure⁹. Dong which is one of the study locations is made up of predominantly Christians of Bachama ethnicity who also understand and speak Hausa language⁹. Facilities in this community include schools, a

market square and a health center among others. On the other hand, Numan LGA has an area of 905km² with a population of about 122,300 projected with 2006 census figure¹⁰. Kikan which is one of the study locations is made up of predominantly Christians of the Bachama ethnicity who also understand and speak Hausa language¹⁰. The major occupation in both communities is farming (including fishing) and trading^{9,10}.

Study population

The population to be assessed was 120 pupils, aged 4-12 years, their caregivers (parents and blood relatives) and the 6 teachers.

Ethical Consideration

Permission was sought and granted by the Adamawa State Ministry of Health, Yola and this study was sponsored by Partners West Africa Nigeria (PWAN) a non-governmental organization (NGO) registered with the Nigeria Corporate Affairs Commission (CAC) and saddled with the responsibilities of running a non-conventional educational programme for children amidst extreme armed conflict. The NGO is engaging Children to Counter Violent Extremism (ECCVE-II) by expanding opportunities through improving the quality of life for children by arts, numeracy, literacy, education and fun.

Inclusion Criteria

All care givers of the pupils that were present and who gave oral consent to participate were interviewed via consecutive sampling method. Assent was also received for each pupil engaged in the informal educational programme. However, only 117 pupils were present as one was ill the other had not returned from holidays and the last had been removed from the programme

The Instruments

Short Sociodemographic instrument- for the biodata of the participants- it assessed the age and sex of the children, and their classes.

Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ)- This is a brief and short emotional and behavioural screening tool for ages 4-17 years and it exists in various versions including the parent's report, teacher's report and self-report¹¹. The SDQ consists of 25 items, 14 items describe perceived difficulties, 10 perceived strengths and one is neutral¹¹. Responses include not true, somewhat true and certainly true¹². Perceived difficulties responses are scored 0-2 while perceived strengths are scored in the reverse¹². The 25 SDQ items are divided into scales of emotional problems, conduct problems, hyperactivity problems, peer problems and prosocial scale (five items per scale). The emotional subscale measures emotionality of a child as rated by either parents or teacher. The other subscale such as conduct measures conduct and behaviour, hyperactivity measures the activity level of the individual child, while the peer relationship subscale measures the level of child relationship with his or her peers. The combination of the emotional, conduct, hyperactivity and peer relationship problems gives the Total Difficulties Scores (TDS). A score is calculated for each scale (range 0-10) and a total difficulty score for the four scales (excluding prosocial behaviour)¹². The prosocial subscale measures the social skill and general resilience factor inherent in the child that can serve as a protective source for the child to overcome challenges. Additional questions on impact of the difficulties enquire about chronicity, distress, social impairment and burden for others¹³. This is also known as the supplementary part of the SDQ. The SDQ and its subscales are then further classified as Normal, Borderline and Abnormal¹² based on the cut off marks set by the originator, Goodman^{11,12}. The SDQ, has been used in different population of children and adolescent and has been shown to have good psychometric properties¹².

Procedure

The pupils in the non-conventional school were divided into three, based on their respective classes I-III (class I comprise of grade 1 and 2, class II comprises of grades 3 and 4 while class III comprises of grades 5 and 6). The interview was conducted in each class together with the

respective teachers as each child comes in and being accompanied by a parent or blood relative to ensure privacy.

Questionnaires were administered via face to face interview minimizing the risks of errors and to ensure homogeneity of questioning and it was filled in by the researchers who were trained consultant Psychiatrists fluent in both English and Hausa languages.

The SDQ parents' and teacher's version was administered to the child's parent/ blood relative and the latter to the teachers. The data was collected over a week.

Data analysis

The Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 25 (SPSS-25) Software package was used to analyze the data. The results were presented in frequency tables, mean, standard deviation and descriptive analysis. T-test was used to compare mean values of numerical variables and Chi Square test was used to investigate the difference between categorical variables and their associations. Values of $P < 0.05$ were considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

Socio-demographic characteristics of pupils in both locations

A total of 117 pupils were enrolled into the study, with 59 (50.4%) and 58(49.6) from Dong and Kikan communities respectively. Their ages range between 4 and 14 years inclusive, with mean ages of 9.79 ± 2.35 and 9.74 ± 2.49 for Dong and Kikan, respectively. The mean ages of the two groups did not differ significantly ($t=0.009$, $p=0.992$). Gender distribution between the two locations was unequal, with more males in both communities ($X^2=3.87$, $p=0.049$). See table 1.

Prevalence and pattern of emotional and behavioural problems in children who experienced armed attacks as rated by the parents

Based on the cut off points as recommended by Goodman¹² the children were classified as shown in table 2 and 3 into normal, borderline, abnormal and further into borderline/ abnormal categories in different scales of the SDQ.

Under the Total difficulties subscale (TDS) of the SDQ, 14 (13.1%) of the children in both locations were classified as having borderline/ abnormal using cut off of 5-10 as rated by the parents. A total of 35 (30%) parents in both locations rated their children as having borderline/abnormal with emotional problems. With respect to conduct problems subscale, 13(11.1%) of all parent rated their children as having borderline problems. Seven (6.0%), and as many as 33(28.2%) of all parents rated their children as having borderline/abnormal difficulties in hyperactivity and peer problem scales. See table 2.

Table1: Socio-demographic characteristics of the pupils in both locations

Variable	Location		
	Frequency (%)		
	Dong (n=59)	Kikan(=58)	Total(N=117)
Age Group			
0-5	2(40.0)	3(60.0)	5(100)
6-10	32(53.3)	28(46.7)	60(100)
11>	25(48.1)	27(51.9)	52(100)
Mean age \pm SD	9.79 \pm 2.35	9.74 \pm 2.49	9.87 \pm 2.85
Gender			
Male	41(57.7)	30(42.3)	71(100)
Female	18(39.1)	28(60.9)	46 (100)

Mean age difference: $t=0.009$, $p=0.992$, Gender difference: $X^2=3.87$, $p=0.049$

Table 2: Distribution of various subscales of Strength and difficulties in both Locations, based on parents' SDQ rating scale

Variable	Frequency(n)			Statistics	P
	Dong (n=59)	Kikan (n=58)	Total (n=117)		
Emotion	n (%)	n (%)	N (%)	0.792	0.673
Normal	42(51.2)	40(48.8)	82(100)		
Borderline	10(55.6)	8(44.4)	18(100)		
Abnormal	7(41.2)	10(58.8)	17(100)		
Conduct				0.838	0.360
Normal	54(51.9)	50(48.9)	104(100)		
Borderline	5(38.5)	8(61.5)	13(100)		
Abnormal	0	0	0		
Hyperactivity				0.325	0.850
Normal	55(50.0)	55(0.0)	110(100)		
Borderline	2(50.0)	2(50.0)	4(100)		
Abnormal	2(66.7)	1(33.3)	3(100)		
Peer problem				5.897	0.052
Normal	48(57.1)	36(42.9)	84(100)		
Borderline	3(25.0)	9(75.0)	12(100)		
Abnormal	8(38.1)	13(61.9)	21(100)		
Total Difficulties Score				2.679	0.262
Normal	53(51.5)	50(48.5)	103(100)		
Borderline	3(30.0)	7(70.0)	10(100)		
Abnormal	3(75.0)	1(25.0)	4(100)		
Strength(prosocial)Score				-	-
Normal	59(50.4)	58(49.9)	117(100)		
Borderline	-	-	-		
Abnormal	-	-	-		

Table 3: Distribution of various domains of Strength and difficulties in both Locations, based on Teachers' rating

Variable	Frequency (%) Location		Total	Statistics	
	Dong(n=59)	Kikan(n=58)		X ²	P
Emotional					
Normal	46(54.8)	38(45.2)	84(100)	2.877	0.237
Borderline	4(30.8)	9(69.2)	13(100)		
Abnormal	9(45.0)	11(55.0)	20(100)		
Conduct					
Normal	51(51.5)	48(48.5)	99(100)	3.083	0.214
Borderline	1(16.7)	5(83.3)	6(100)		
Abnormal	7(58.3)	5(41.7)	12(100)		
Hyperactivity					
Normal	52(51.5)	49(48.5)	101(100)	1.477	0.478
Borderline	5(55.6)	4(44.4)	9(100)		
Abnormal	2(28.6)	5(71.4)	7(100)		
Peer problem					
Normal	47(51.6)	44(48.4)	91(100)	1.940	0.379
Borderline	9(56.2)	7(43.8)	16(100)		
Abnormal	3(30.0)	7(70.0)	10(100)		
Difficulty Score					
Normal	46(56.1)	36(43.9)	82(100)	4.040	0.133
Borderline	6(31.6)	13(68.4)	19(100)		
Abnormal	7(43.8)	9(56.2)	16(100)		
Strength (Prosocial)Score					
Normal	59(50.4)	58(49.6)	117(100)	--	--
Borderline	0	0	0		
Abnormal	0	0	0		

Table 4: Distribution of the overall difficulties (impact) in more than one area of life as rated by parents as a supplementary part of the SDQ

Variable	Dong=n (%)	Kikan=n (%)	Total=n (%)
Overall difficulties in ≥1 area			
NO	53(51.5)	50(48.5)	103(100)
Minor difficulties	4(40)	6(60.0)	10(100)
Definite difficulties	2(50.0)	2(50.0)	4(100)
Severe difficulties	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)
Total(N=117)	59	58	117(100)
Duration of difficulties			
Less than a month	0(0)	1(100)	1(100)
1-5months	0(0)	2(100)	2(100)
6-12months	1(25.0)	3(75.0)	4(100)
Over a year	5(71.4)	2(28.6)	7(100)
Upset or distress to child			
Not at all	1(50.0)	1(50.0)	2(100)
Only a little	2(33.3)	4(66.7)	6(100)
Quite a lot	2(40.0)	3(60.0)	5(100)
A great deal	1(100)	0(0)	1(100)
Difficulties in home life			
Not at all	2(50.0)	2(50.0)	4(100)
Only a little	4(50.0)	4(50.0)	8(100)
Quite a lot	0(0)	1(100)	1(100)
A great deal	0(0)	1(100)	1(100)
Difficulties in friendships			
Not at all	4(57.1)	3(42.9)	7(100)
Only a little	2(33.3)	4(66.7)	6(100)
Quite a lot	0(0.0)	1(100)	1(100)
A great deal	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)
Difficulties in learning			
Not at all	2(20.0)	8(80.8)	10(100)
Only a little	2(100)	0(0)	2(100)
Quite a lot	2(100)	0(0)	2(100)
A great deal	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)
Difficulties in leisure activities			
Not at all	5(62.5)	3(37.5)	8(100)
Only a little	1(33.3)	2(66.7)	3(100)
Quite a lot	0(0)	3(100)	3(100)
A great deal	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)
Burden of difficulties on the family			
Not at all	2(28.6)	5(71.4)	7(100)
Only a little	2(50.0)	2(50.0)	4(100)
Quite a lot	2(66.7)	1(33.3)	3(100)
A great deal	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)

Borderline and abnormal emotional scale cut off points=5-10
 Borderline and abnormal conduct problem scale cut off points=3-10
 Borderline and abnormal hyperactivity scale cut off points=6-10
 Borderline and abnormal peer relationship problem cut of points=4-10
 Normal pro-social scale cut off points=6-10

Prevalence and pattern of emotional and behavioural problems in children who experienced armed attacks as rated by the teachers

A total of 35 (30.0%) children were rated borderline/abnormal on the total difficulty subscale by their Teachers. Thirty- three (28.2%), 18(15.4%) and 26(22.2%) children in both locations were rated by their teachers as having borderline/abnormal difficulties in emotional, conduct and hyperactivity subscales respectively. So also, were 26(22.2%) with borderline/abnormal peer relationship problems. See table 3.

Borderline and abnormal emotional scale cut off points=5-10
 Borderline and abnormal conduct problem scale cut off points=3-10
 Borderline and abnormal hyperactivity scale cut off points=6-10
 Borderline and abnormal peer relationship problem cut of points=4-10
 Normal pro-social scale cut off points=6-10

In table 4, out of the 117 pupils enrolled into the study, 103(88.0%) had no overall difficulties in one or more areas of life on the supplementary of the SDQ. The rest, 14(12.0%) were rated by their parents as having one or more difficulties in some areas of their lives, lasting at least one month, with 10(71.4%) of them having these difficulties causing distress to themselves. Similarly, 10(71.4%) and 7(50.0%) of the 14 children in both locations had difficulties in their home life and friendship as rated by their parents. A total of 4(28.6%) had difficulties in learning (all in Dong community).

In table 5, out of the 117 pupils enrolled into the study, 91(78.6%) had no overall difficulties in one or more areas of life while 25(21.4%) had it, lasting at least less than one month. Out of the 25 with overall difficulties, 21(84.0%) were rated by their teachers as having one or more difficulties in some areas of their lives, lasting at least one month. The difficulties caused distress in 21(71.4%) of the 25 children. Similarly, 19(76.0%) and

15(60.0%) of the 25 children had their difficulties interfering with peer relationship and classroom learning, while 15(60.0%) had difficulties that interfered with their overall activities.

Comparing the ratings by parents and teachers on the children in the two locations.

Table 6 below shows that the SDQ total mean scores for the children as rated by their parents and Teachers in both communities did not differ significantly ($t=0.103, p=0.918$)

Table 5: Distribution of the overall difficulties in ≥ areas of life as rated by their Teachers as the supplementary part of the SDQ.

Variable	Dong	Kikan	Total
NO	54(58.7)	38(41.3)	92(100)
Minor difficulties	3(27.3)	8(72.7)	11(100)
Definite difficulties	2(15.4)	11(84.6)	13(100)
Severe difficulties	0(0)	1(100)	1(100)
Total(N=117)			117(100)
Duration of difficulties			
Less than a month	0(0)	4(100)	4(100)
1-5months	0(0)	7(100)	7(100)
6-12months	5(45.5)	5(54.5)	10(100)
Over a year	0(0)	3(100)	3(100)
Upset or distress to child			
Not at all	0(0)	4(100)	4(100)
Only a little	4(36.4)	7(63.6)	11(100)
Quite a lot	1(10.0)	9(9.0)	10(100)
A great deal	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)
Interference with peer relationship			
Not at all	1(16.7)	5(83.3)	6(100)
Only a little	2(20.0)	8(10.0)	10(100)
Quite a lot	2(22.2)	7(77.8)	9(100)
A great deal	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)
Interference with classroom learning			
Not at all	0(0)	6(100)	6(100)
Only a little	2(22.2)	7(77.8)	9(100)
Quite a lot	3(30.0)	7(70.0)	10(100)
A great deal	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)
overall activities			
Not at all	1(10.0)	9(90.0)	10(100)
Only a little	0(0)	2(100)	2(100)
Quite a lot	4(50.0)	4(40)	8(100)
A great deal	0(0)	5(100)	5(100)

Table 6: Comparison of SDQ total mean scores between Parents and Teachers

Location	Mean score	Standard Deviation	T	P
Dong	16.02	4.53	0.103	0.918
Kikan	16.10	4.55		

DISCUSSION

The tragedy of traumatic events experienced by children and adults as an aftermath of violent armed conflicts across the globe has been recognized to affect mental wellbeing and behaviour^{3,4}. Our research was aimed at finding the prevalence of behavioural and emotional changes or problems or consequences in children who had experience

violent armed attacks and the difficulties inherent in school learning, education and engaging the communities. There were 120 children that were enrolled in the schools for the two communities (Kikan and Dong in Demsa and Numan Local government Areas of Adamawa in North East, Nigeria, respectively) but only 117 children's behavior were rated by the parents and teachers using the Strength and Difficulty questionnaire because one child was ill during the period of assessment, another had not returned from the holidays and the last had been withdrawn from the program.

Socio-demographics of pupils at the non-conventional schools

The mean ages of the pupil were 9.79 ± 2.35 and 9.74 ± 2.49 in both communities with no significant differences. The mean age as found in our study falls within the middle childhood age group (9-11years) of children developmental milestones. The middle childhood is often characterized by the child growing independence from the family; increase in peer pressure and feeling good about themselves which may make them to be able to resist negative pressures and to make better choices for themselves. Children within this middle childhood age group also face more academic challenges and view others point of view more clearly by either internalizing or externalizing such views. The experience of trauma by the pupils in our study and falling within the middle childhood developmental milestones may result in them having an unconscious organization of belief that will determine how these children see the world in the future and how they choose to act or relate with it². In this same age group, they also have increase attention span which may be disturbed as an aftermath of experiencing violet extremism, as evidenced by increased hyperactivity and this may lead to poor academic achievements.

Our study found a difference in the gender distribution in the two schools with more boys being enrolled than

girls. This finding is in keeping with the general school enrollment trend in Northern Nigeria and especially in the North Eastern part of the country which has only about 47.7% of the girl child being enrolled into primary schools¹⁴. This confirmed the inequality experienced by the girl child which may lead to various forms of emotional dysregulations, decrease opportunities in life, poor resilience factor and lack of skill to handle life time issues.

Prevalence of Emotional and Behavioural Problems as Rated by Both Parents and Teachers

The prevalence of emotional and behavioural problems as indicated by the total difficulties scores (TDS) of the Strength and Difficulty Questionnaire (SDQ) as rated by individual parents, fourteen (12%) parents rated their children to have borderline/ abnormal difficulties while the teachers rated 31 (26.5%) pupils to have borderline/ abnormal difficulties on the TDS. The TDS is an indication that the children have emotional behavioral problems, conduct and hyperactivity problems, and peer relationship problems that may create difficulties and distress to the child in learning and having fun within the school environment and the community. From the above finding the teachers' rating is at variance with parental rating of children total difficulties on the SDQ. However, the difference in parents and teachers mean scores was not statistically significant. This suggests that either of the two raters could be relied on in future rating. A possible explanation for the differences, though not found to be significant is that home situations for the children most often is not tasking as that of the school, where new things are to be learnt and making adjustment to adopt to school's environment is highly needed. It is worthy to note that these difficulties are neutralized by the high 'normal' finding on the Pro-social Subscale of the SDQ which measures the social skills and general resilience inherent in an individual child. The strength scale is a positive finding that will mitigate the effect of trauma on the child and his learning ability and also on the development of mental health problems either at present or later in life.

Taking cognizance of the individual subscales of the SDQ, we found that about a third of the children have both emotional and peer relationship problems whereas, about one tenth of the children had conduct and hyperactivity problems. However, the rating by the teachers showed subtle differences as compared with the parents' rating. These findings are maybe indicative that learning and education may be difficult to be attained by these children. The reasons for these may not be too farfetched. Not conducting oneself in school well as occasion with truancy, delinquency and stubbornness may lead to having friction with the school authority thereby, creating a tense environment that may not favour excellent learning and educational processes. Hyperactive child may have inattention with declining academic achievements. Increase level of hyperactivity often make the child to be 'on the go-like movement' which may bring him or her into poor peer relationship problems with others. As such, other children may not understand the individual child, leading to ostracization from play grounds. This may affect fun play and arts which are integral part of learning and education. A child with emotional problems may have difficulty remember things he was thought and he or she may be moody in class and at play grounds. Having emotional problems may also lead to serious depressive or other emotional problems or difficulties such as mania or deliberate self-harm, suicide etc.

The above findings on the TDS of SDQ and various subscales are in keeping with a study on the impact of natural disaster¹⁵ versus a spate of communal riots in Gurajat, India,¹⁶ which showed only 7.6% of children affected by the earthquake fell into the abnormal score on the TDS of the SDQ. That is, comparing it with parental rating. But it is dissimilar when teachers' rating was considered. However, studies by Thabet et al,¹⁷ found about 43% of Palestine children who were exposed to shelling (extreme violent) had abnormal scores on the TDS of the SDQ which is in similar with the teachers' rating in our study. The disproportionate finding between our study and theirs, that is, the parental rating and Thabet et al could be due to the difference in duration of exposure to trauma and

the time of carrying out the research. While their study was carried out about a month after the traumatic events, our study was carried two years after the incidence. Previous research showed that there is an inverse relationship between the time of exposure to trauma and the development of abnormal behavior³. Quite often than not, is the fact that time heals³.

Children's Strength (prosocial) as rated by both parents and teachers

Despite the parents' and teachers' reports of the difficulties in the children/ pupils, the children had 100% normal scores on the prosocial scale which an indication of 'normal strength' as shown in the pro-social scale of the SDQ. This maybe an indication that there are general resilience factors in these children/ pupils and it is a positive factor that could be exploited to help in mitigating emotional and behavioural problems that is attributed to difficulties in learning and education. If utilize well it will help in mitigating any future mental health problems that may aroused.

The impact of difficulties in more than one area of life

Our study found that the violent attacks created difficulties that were more impactful on one of the communities (Kikan). The impact of the difficulties were measured in terms of the duration of the difficulties faced by the child; the distress the child may have as a result of the attacks; impact on developing friendship and relationship; the difficulties in learning in the classroom; difficulties at home and family; difficulties engaging in leisure activities i.e., having fun, doing arts and playing). The plausible reason for the difference in our finding between the two communities, is that, Kikang had more than fair share of the attacks as compared to the other community. Too much of exposure to armed conflicts with little or no time to heal may reinforce stress and difficulties. These difficulties may affect the learning and education of the child, thereby, affecting him or her to exploit opportunities to improve his or her quality of life.

CONCLUSION

The study revealed that traumatic events from extreme armed attacks experienced by children attending a non-conventional school impact on the emotion and behaviour and this may negatively impact on their learning and education. With poor educational attainment the utilization of capacity and potential to expands opportunities will hinder leading to poor engagement in good governance, accountability and transparency.

Recommendation

Psychosocial interventions should be carried out within these communities through the following means-

1. Formulating an advocacy program for peace and conflict resolution with emphasis on forgiveness so that there can be a future generation of peace makers to break the cycle of violence
2. Build a safe environment where the people can have a sense of safety by promoting neighbourhood/ community watch
3. Creation of age-group related social support network among inhabitants of the communities whereby various age group can interact with peers on issues of common interest
4. Construction of social play grounds/groups within the communities to help children play-reenact their fears and worries from within which helps to diffuse the tension and help with relaxing.
5. Incorporate school-based mental health programs into the school curriculum which will include art-play / therapy, teaching of students how to develop and improve in their social skills in relating with peers and teachers. The school program will also involve training teachers on basic skills in identifying strength and difficulties of a child and how to work on each child's positive factor in re-shaping the child's behaviours.
6. Establishment of community-based mental health programs by scaling down knowledge of mental health to the primary health managers within the community for early identification of people with mental health

- needs and referral to appropriate quarters.
7. Skill acquisition and vocational training to enable members of the communities to become independent and productive.
 8. Establishment of trauma healing centers for the communities that will cater for the needs of the community

Limitation of the study

The study is a descriptive one and causal and effect relationship cannot be established with such study. Socially desirable responses in a psychosocial study often brings biases into analysis of the true intension of the responders and this will make generalization difficult. No initial normative data prior to the armed attacks to compare with the findings and deduce the changes found.

Conflict of interest

All the authors were contacted and sponsored by Partners West Africa Nigeria (PWAN) an NGO financially to carried out psychosocial assessment of the two schools in Kikan and Dong of Demsa and Numan local Government Areas of Adamawa state, North-Eastern Nigeria, respectively.

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